

A Comparative Study of Different Classification Algorithms for the Prediction of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)

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Abstract- *Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a long-term disorder in which the kidneys gradually degrade and stop working. This illness has grown into one of the world's most critical public health problems. It's a stealthy disease that's often only detected when it's too late due to test anomalies. The major goal of this research is to employ different classification algorithms on a patient's medical information to assess whether they have chronic kidney disease. This study compares several algorithms for predicting chronic kidney disease. Some well-known machine learning techniques used for chronic kidney disease prediction include Random Forest, XGBoost, Logistic Regression, and Naive Bayes Classifier. Here, we aim to create a sequential model trying to predict CKD. The results of the experiments demonstrate that sequential model generates an accuracy of 97.19%, which is less when compared with the accuracy of Random Forest and XGBoost.*

Keywords- *chronic kidney disease;sequential model;neural network;accuracy;precision;*

I. INTRODUCTION

Data science is a process that involves analysing and extracting knowledge from large amounts of data. It can be used in various fields such as healthcare, social science, and machine translation. Today, data science has gained widespread recognition in various academic and applied research arenas.

In the healthcare industry, classification is a well-known data mining strategy. It's used to figure out what class each data point belongs to. Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbour, and Naive Bayes are some of the categorization algorithms.

CKD normally develops slowly and with few symptoms, and many individuals are unaware they have it until the illness is advanced [11,12,13,14]. When

compared to breast or prostate cancer, this illness kills a larger number of people each year. The ability to foresee the presence of this disease is critical for taking the required precautions.

And this research paper implements and analyses the Sequential model, which is a simple Neural network to predict CKD. A comparative analysis is done on Sequential model.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] N V Ganapathi Raju, K Prasanna Lakshmi, K. Gayathri Praharsitha, Chittampalli Likhitha, they used multiple machine learning models to predict chronic kidney disease, such as support vector machine, random forest, XGBoost, logistic regression and naive bayes. And they concluded that Random Forest and XGBoost outperform other categorization methods.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. *Acquire:* Patient medical information acquired from several laboratories in Tamil Nadu through the UCI repository was used to create the database for CKD prediction. Blood pressure, pus cells, sugar, specific gravity, age, albumin, serum creatinine, red blood cells, bacteria, cell count, blood glucose random, blood urea, sodium, potassium, hemoglobin, packed cell volume, white blood diabetes mellitus, and anemia are among the 400 records with 25 different attributes related to kidney disease.
2. *Data pre-processing:* The target labels for the CKD dataset classes are "ckd" and "nckd." To replace categorical values with numbers, we use numbers such as "1" and "0" to the data so that the algorithms could operate on it. This procedure is repeated for the other characteristics that contain strings.

Many unknown values have been uncovered in the CKD dataset. These are initially replaced with integers. The medians of each column are then used to fill in the missing values in each column.

3. *Data Exploration:* Data exploration is done at the start of the data analysis, When a data analyst uses various visual scrutinising methodologies rather than typical data management tools to try to grasp what is in a dataset and the properties of the data.

i. Univariate data analysis:

It is the depiction of data in a graphical format. The top characteristics found after doing univariate feature selection are depicted in the ggplot below. Ggplot is a python graphics library used to produce visualizations.

- a. Ggplot: depicts the relationship between attributes as a visual representation.

Fig 1: ggplot

- b. The value distributions of all the characteristics are represented in the graphs below.

Fig 2.1(age)

Fig 2.2(bp)

Fig 2.3(sg)

Fig 2.4(al)

Fig 2.5(su)

Fig 2.6(bgr)

Fig 2.7(bu)

Fig 2.8(su)

Fig 2.9(sod)

Fig 2.10(pot)

Fig 2.11(hemo)

Fig 2.12(pcv)

Fig 2.13(wc)

Fig 2.14(rc)

ii. Bi-variant analysis:

The connection serves as the foundation for our investigation. Quantities have a reciprocal connection. Correlation can assist in the prediction of one quantity based on another. Using the describe function, you may discover the relationship between variables. Heat maps may be used to visualize the association. The heat map below shows the correlation between all of the dataset's properties. The correlation of all qualities is depicted in the above heat map. The correlation is measured on a scale, with the correlation and value determined by the color intensity.

Fig -3: Correlation between different predictors

4. **Feature Selection:** Feature selection is used to reduce training and assessment times while also increasing prediction accuracy. One of the ways is model-based ranking, which involves fitting a classifier to each feature and evaluating the prediction power. This strategy chooses the strongest traits one at a time but overlooks the predictive value of combining features. After utilizing univariate feature selection to explore the CKD dataset, the features whose contribution is almost comparable to the contribution of all the characteristics combined are discovered. The main features are "hemo", "sg.", "sc", "pcv" and "rbcc"

5. **Model selection:** As mentioned above, we are using sequential model for predicting CKD.

(i) **LR:** A process known as logistic regression is used to forecast a categorical dependent variable. It can be performed by forecasting the output of this variable from a set of variables. Since it is a method that predicts the outcome of a given situation, it can be called a categorical or discrete method. However, instead of giving a definite number, it returns probabilistic values. In terms of application, Logistic Regression and Linear Regression are very similar. Regression issues are solved using Linear Regression, whereas classification problems are solved using Logistic Regression.

(ii) **SVM:** support vector machine organizes data into two groups. It is trained using a collection of data that has already been classified into two categories, and it constructs the model as it learns. The task of an SVM algorithm is to determine which category a new data point belongs to. SVM is

characterized as a non-binary linear classifier because of this. Not only should an SVM algorithm sort items into categories, but it should also leave as much space between them on a network as possible.

(iii) **XGB:** XGBoost stands for “Extreme Gradient Boosting”. XGBoost is a distributed gradient boosting toolkit that has been tuned for efficiency, flexibility, and portability. It uses the Gradient Boosting framework to create Machine Learning algorithms. It uses parallel tree boosting to tackle a wide range of data science issues quickly and accurately.

(iv) **NB:** Naive Bayes is one of the most basic and powerful classification algorithms based on the Bayes Theorem and the premise of predictor independence. The Naive Bayes classifier posits that a feature's existence in a class is unrelated to the presence of any other feature. For binary and multi-class classification issues, Naive Bayes is a classification algorithm.

(v) **RF:** Random Forest is also known as Decision Tree Forest. It's a well-known decision tree-based ensemble model. These models are more accurate than other decision trees. Both classification and regression applications employ this approach. We generate a vast number of decision trees in a random forest, and each decision tree is fed with each observation. The most common outcome for each observation is the final output. By feeding a fresh observation into all the trees, we get a majority vote for each categorization model.

(vi) **Sequential Model -** Sequential model is just a Keras Layers composition that is linear. The sequential model is simple, basic, and capable of representing almost all existing neural networks. Each Keras layer in the Keras model is comparable to a layer in the real proposed neural network architecture (input layer, hidden layer, and output layer). Keras provides with a large number of pre-built layers, making the creation of any complicated neural network quick and easy.

IV. RESULT

The experiment was done on Google Colab. Its goal is to make package management and distribution easier. The performance variables for classification, such as accuracy, precision, and f1score, are used to analyze classification algorithms. The result shows that the sequential model can classify patients with ckd and nockd based on the dataset given. The model provides correct result with good accuracy.

When we looked at the accuracy of the experimental outcomes, we observed that sequential model was 97.19% accurate.

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Precision :0.9454545454545454  
Recall :1.0  
Threshold : 0.5587652  
F1 Score : 0.9719626168224299
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V. CONCLUSION

We examined the effectiveness of five classifiers in predicting CKD prognosis. The goal of this study is to look at classification methods for CKD analysis and prediction. In terms of classification accuracy, the experimental findings of our suggested technique showed that sequential model performed less than other algorithms such as RF and XGB for the dataset under consideration.

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